

TECHNOLOGICAL TRANSFER AND PERFORMANCE OF MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN LAGOS

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ABSTRACT

Technology transfer and performance of manufacturing firms is a research study conducted to evaluate the effects of vertical and horizontal technology transfers on profitability and productivity of selected firms in Lagos, Nigeria. The basic variables of the study are vertical transfer, horizontal transfer, profitability and productivity, which were derived from the objectives of the study. A sample of two hundred and fifteen (215) was randomly drawn from six judgmentally selected organizations in Lagos, using questionnaire. The resulting primary data were analyzed for correlations and multiple regressions using the version 20 of the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS). The results were that vertical technology transfer had positive effects on the manufacturing firms' profitability ($r = 0.816$) and productivity ($r = 0.625$). Horizontal transfer had similar significant positive effects with $r = 0.741$ for productivity and $r = 0.566$ for profitability. All beta coefficients from the regression result were positive and statistically significant. The coefficient of multiple determination from the model summary was $R^2 = 0.321$, with an adjusted value of 0.294, showing that vertical and horizontal transfers would have a joint effect of 29.4% increase in profitability and productivity. These findings led to the conclusion that technology transfer has a positive effect on a firm's performance and to the recommendation that managers of manufacturing firms should adopt technology transfer as a strategy towards higher profitability and productivity, among others.

Keywords: Vertical transfer, horizontal transfer, profitability, productivity performance, technology transfer.

Introduction

Technology transfer is the movement of accumulated knowledge developed by a specific organization to other organizations. It involves the physical and electronic dissemination of skills, techniques, product samples, finished products/service and intellectual property rights from an origination firm to recipients. It takes place between universities, firms, organizations, countries or even continents.

The model of technological transfers is not specifically the same among nations. While the developing countries tend to follow a model that produce technology products before research is embarked on them, advanced countries tend to embark on research first before developing the product, as proped by Amsten (1989) and cited by Ramanathan (2020).

Whichever dimension technological transfer takes, its essence remains to make it available in areas where it is needed, at a profit to both the transferer and transferee. In this perspective, two modes of transfer have been identified-vertical transfer and horizontal transfer (Grosse, 1996). It is said to be vertical if it follows the route from basic research to applied research to development and finally to production. On the other hand, horizontal technologies transfer involves movement of technology from point of its origin to other organizations, countries or regions.

Both the vertical and horizontal modes of transfer are supposed to better the performance of the transferring organization and the recipient alike. By performance we mean the state of wellness of the organization with regards to its set goals. Performance is measured using various yardsticks, in this study, profitability and productivity are used which means the capacity of the firm to make profits and the ratio of inputs to output respectively.

Since technology transfer benefits both parties, it is supposed to be positively correlated with a firm's performance. However, this can be verified by an empirical investigation of this kind. This study therefore examines technology transfer and performance of manufacturing firms in Lagos.

Statement of the Problem

The controversial nature of technological transfer calls for its evaluation with respect to contribution to organizational performance. While some countries rely on indigenous technology and transfers are purely domestic, others rely almost absolutely on foreign acquisition of technology product. Some argue that some of the acquired technologies can actually be produced locally by concerted effort, others maintain that transferred technology is cheaper in the comparative cost analysis. Admittedly a foreign organization that manufactures a technological product needs to transfer its product to make a profit under patent rights. Much as the receiving country needs the technology for its own productivity. This makes technology transfer necessary in theoretical perspective. An empirical study is needed to examine this. For this reason this study evaluates the effects of vertical and horizontal technology transfers on organizational profitability and productivity using some manufacturing firms in Lagos as reference points.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

- i. Examine the effects of vertical technology transfer on organizational productivity.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between vertical technology transfer and organizational profitability.
- iii. Identify the effects of horizontal technology transfer on organizational productivity.
- iv. Determine the relationship between horizontal technology transfer and organizational profitability.

1.4 Research Questions

The questions asked in line in the objectives of the study are as follows:

- i. What are the effects of vertical transfer on organizational productivity?
- ii. To what extent is vertical transfer related to profitability?
- iii. In what ways is horizontal transfer related to organizational productivity?
- iv. What are the effects of horizontal transfer on profitability?

Research Hypotheses

The hypotheses formulated to guide the attainment of the objective are stated in null form as follows:

Ho1: Vertical technology transfer has no significant effect on organization's productivity.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between vertical transfer and organizational profitability.

Ho3: Horizontal technology transfer has no significant relationship with organizational productivity.

Ho4: There is no significant relationship between horizontal transfer and organizational profitability.

Significance of the Study

Stakeholders to the study include business managers, employees, research scholars and research institutions.

Business managers will find the findings and recommendation of the study invaluable in the process of taking decisions that pertain to vertical and horizontal transfers of technologies.

Employees will learn from the study the rationale for technology transfer and the role they are to play in order to achieve high profitability and productivity in the process.

To scholars, researchers and research institutions, the study provides academic resource that could be tapped for further studies or reference purpose.

Scope of the Study

The study dwelt on horizontal and vertical transfers of technology as well as organizational profitability and productivity. Other variables than the ones mentioned here are considered to fall outside the scope of the research. Secondly, the geographic scope of the study was Lagos. Possibly, all organization's outside Lagos may not possess the same characteristics of Lagos firms that led to the findings of the study.

Review of related Literature

Scholarly articles, textbooks extracts and other publications related to technology transfer and/or organizational performance are reviewed in this section.

Concept of Technology Transfer

Spiegel (2007) defines technology transfers as a mechanism by which the accumulated knowledge developed by a specific organization is transferred wholly or partly to another entity to allow the receiver to benefit from such knowledge.

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The New Business Dictionary (2020) defines technology transfer as the movement of a new technology from the origination to a secondary user, especially from developed to developing countries in an attempt to boost their economics.

Grosse (1996) defines technology transfer in a similar way with Spiegel (2007) by stating that technology transfer is the process of disseminating technology from the person or organization that owns or holds it to another person or organization.

According to Gross (1996), technology transfer occurs along various axes: among universities, from university to businesses, from large businesses to small ones, from governments to businesses and vice versa; as well as across geographical borders. Items being transferred include research findings, skills, techniques, procedures, innovations, manufactured product samples, intellectual property rights and information packages. Grosse identifies two major modes of transfer-vertical transfer and horizontal transfers.

Vertical Transfer

Vertical transfer is the movement of technology from basic research to applied research, to development and then to production in that order. It is a transfer that begins with fundamental research about the product or service being conceived. The diagram below is schematic illustration of vertical transfer.

Basic Research → applied → research → development → production

Ramanathan (2020) argues that vertical transfer pertains essentially to developed countries. According to him, most developing countries often tend to produce the product and proceed to research (reverse vertical).

Horizontal Transfer

Horizontal transfer is the movement of technology used in one place, organization or context to another place, organization or context (Gross, 1996). Technological transfers that go on all over the world today among countries belong to this mode of transfer. It involves physical and electronic movement of products samples, finished products, skills techniques, information, intellectual property, etc, from one organization or country to another. Gross notes that most horizontal transfers originate from advanced countries and proceed to the developing ones.

Concept of Firm's Performance

Mohammed and Saif (2019) defined performance as a measures of how well an organization realizes its operational goals in relation with set standards. Performance is measured using various induces such as profitability, productivity, shareholders wealth, revenue, customers subscription/patronage, etc.

Profitability

Profitability is the capacity of a firm to make profit. Profit is the difference in amount between revenue and costs. Profits is measured in various ways which include return on assets, return on investment, net profit margin, gross profit margin etc. since technological transfers is suppose to raise the revenue of the firms, it is supposed to increase the profit of the firm provided cost s are not excessively incurred.

Productivity

Productivity is the ratio of input to output. It is a measure of how efficiently resources are transformed to end products using the available time, human and material resources. Productivity is an important index in determining the performance of manufacturing firms.

Technology Transfer Model-The Amsden Model

Amsden (1989) argues that while in developed countries the technology product cycle takes a route that starts with research and end with production; in technologically less advanced countries, the technology product cycle tends to take the route from production and ends with research.

Fig 1: Technology product model
(Source: Amsden 1989, cited by Ramanathan 2020)

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According to Amsden (1989) technology product route that starts from research and terminates with production guarantees a more reliable, scientifically proven and standardized product. This contrasts with what happens when products are made by more of guess and then allowed to enter into research, as common in developing countries.

Empirical Review

Although technology transfer is not fundamentally a business discipline, many scholars in business field have researched on it. Howard & Kamal (2019) studies vertical technology transfer with respect to productivity in Minesota. The study made use of primary data obtained from 712 subjects. The results from the statistical analysis showed that vertical transfer contributed 52.93% changes in productivity ($r = 0.7275$).

Palmberg, Pajerien & Tumo (2017) studied the effects of transferring science based technologies on the economy of Andover, U.S. technological transfers were corrected with the GDP figures for the period 2000 to 2016. The results showed that transfers are beneficial to both the transferer and the transferee and can effect a 26.2% increase in GPD of both parties.

Ramanathan (2020) conducted a study on international technology transfer and its effect on the global economic determinants. The study correlated horizontal transfers with average price levels for the period 2000 to 2019 and found out that the two variables were negatively correlated. The conclusion was that effective horizontal transfer lowers price level.

Methodology

Survey design was used for the study. This involved the interviewing of a selected group of respondents from whom data on technology transfer and organizational performance were obtained using questionnaire as the sampling instrument.

Sampling

From a population of 465 workers of six judgementally selected manufacturing firms in Lagos a sample of 215 was drawn using questionnaire. To provide a guide to the selection of the appropriate sample size, the Taro Yamene's statistical relation was used. This is illustrated below.

$$N = \frac{n}{1+Ne^2} \quad (\text{Yamene 1965, cited by Onuh, 1998})$$

$$= 215$$

Where n is the sample size, e is the error term and N is population size.

Administration Of Instrument

The questionnaire was administrated to the respondents by the researcher after the questionnaire had be validated by research experts and its reliability index determined in a test-retest method that involved a pilot study for a period of two weeks.

Result

Table 4.1 Regression

Var.	Const.	Std. Error	Beta Coeff.	Tolerance	VIF
VT	1.824	0.013	2.148	0.729	1.350
HT	2.041	0.146	2.223	0.929	1.244
PD	0.697	0.002	1.906	0.466	1.263
PF	4.033	1.219	3.411	0.316	1.309
TT	3.172	0.815	1.053	0.488	1.555

Dependent Variables PD, PF

- VT Vertical Transfer
- HT Horizontal Transfer
- PD Productivity
- PF Profitability
- TT Technological Transfer.

Table 4.2 Correlation

Var	VT	HT	PD	PF
VT	1.000			
HT	.518	1.000		
PD	.625	.741	1.000	
PF	.816	.566	.689	1.000

Predictors VT, HT

Table 4.3 Model Summary

Model	Coeff. Of Determine R	R-Square R ²	Adj R ²	Std. Error of Estimate(a)
1	.567	.321	.294	1.0608

Discussion

The regression results in table 4.1 shows beta coefficients of $b_1 = 1.906$, $b_2 = 3.411$ for productivity (PD) and profitability (PE) respectively. The standard errors of the estimate are $\alpha = 0.002$ and $\alpha_2 = 1.219$ respectively, which are insignificant at the 5% level, meaning that the estimation of the regression coefficients was with a reasonable degree of accuracy. The constraint $b_0 = 3.172$, thus, the regression equation is: $TT = 3.172 + 1.906PD + 3.411PF$.

The model summary in table 4.3 shows adjusted coefficient of multiple determination of $R^2 = 0.294$ with a negligible standard error of estimate of $\alpha = 1.0608$. Thus, technological transfer can account for up to 29.4% changes in the productivity and profitability of manufacturing firms.

Table 4.2 shows the correlation results. Vertical transfer (VT) has a significant positive relationship with productivity $r = 0.625$ and profitability $r = 0.816$. Similarly, Horizontal transfer (HT) is significantly related to productivity with $r = 0.741$ and with profitability $r = 0.566$. All coefficients tested significant at both the 5% and 10% levels, indicating high reliability.

These findings led to the rejection of the null hypotheses that there was no significant relationship between vertical/horizontal transfer and productivity/profitability. Howard & Karnial (2019) in an earlier study of organizations in minesota made a finding that vertical technology transfer contributed 52.93% changes in productivity of manufacturing firms in the area. Palmberg, Pajerien & Tuomo (2017) found out that the contribution of technology transfer to GDP figures in and over was as high as 26.2%, Ramanathan (2020) in a study of the effects of technology transfers on the global economy discovered a strong negative correlation between price level and horizontal transfers, indicating that transfer stabilizes global market prices. These earlier findings are in one accord with those of this study.

Conclusion

Vertical technology transfer has positive effects on a manufacturing firm’s productivity and profitability. Vertical transfer can account for 39.06% increase in productivity ($r = 0.625$, $r^2 = 0.3906$) and 66.59% increase in profitability of a firm ($r = 0.816$, $r^2 = 0.6659$). The coefficients obtained from the regression analysis all proved highly significant ($b_0 = 3.172$, $b_1 = 1.906$, $b_2 = 3.411$). These results provide supportive evidence of a significant relationship between the predictive and dependent variables. It is therefore concluded that technology transfer has significant positive effect on a firm performance.

Recommendation

The following recommendations derive from the findings of the study.

- Mangers of manufacturing firms should use technology transfer as a strategy towards higher productivity of the firm.
- Horizontal transfers should strategically handled in a bid to boost productivity since it has been found to have a strong relationship with productivity.
- Managers of indigenouse manufacturing firms should intensify effort at research and development to boost their capacity to make profits from their production business.
- Logistics/procurement management of manufacturing firms should always evaluate the characteristic feature of a transferred technology product as this could affect the reputation of the firm at the deteriment of profit.

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